

Visiting the margins
INnovative CULTural ToUrisM in European peripheries

INCULTUM project is an Innovation Action supported by the European Commission in the frame of the Horizon2020 programme, and coordinated by the University of Granada. INCULTUM deals with the challenges and opportunities of cultural tourism with the aim of furthering sustainable social, cultural and economic development.

The INCULTUM Training Portal (ITP)

ITP is a web-space dedicated to a wide range of targets, including: local stakeholders and communities, university students and researchers, public administrators, business development operators, tourism specialists and cultural heritage managers.

The variety of **training resources** accessible through the portal aim to promote capacity and knowledge of its target users in the areas of sustainable tourism, cultural heritage, innovative participatory approaches, involvement and engagement of living territories and communities.

ITP is an open portal. It hosts training resources developed by the INCULTUM partners as well as collected from organisations and initiatives connected with the INCULTUM network. Resources and links are produced, collected and added to ITP along the whole project life time.

[Discover the resources of ITP](#)

INCULTUM Policy Brief on Sustainable Tourism

INCULTUM Policy Brief on Sustainable Tourism (September 2022) aims at understanding context and challenges for innovatives approaches in tourism to achieve positive social, economic, cultural and environmental impacts.

Cultural Tourism Workshop at EUROMED 2022

This hybrid event is organized in the framework of EUROMED conference in Cyprus, to discuss about the role of community engagement and citizen participation in enhancing and promoting sustainable tourism in

The document formulates **recommendations for the orientation of future research programmes** in the field of cultural tourism, rural heritage management and sustainable development of peripheral territories. The Policy Brief was realized by INCULTUM consortium under coordination of partner Bibracte, dr. Vincent Guichard.

Read more about INCULTUM Policy Development action, and download the Brief:

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peripheral areas that are not often part of the mass tourism itineraries.

INCULTUM - INNOVATIVE CULTURAL TOURISM IN EUROPEAN PERIPHERIES

Wed. 9th November h. 16 EET

This workshop is addressed to cultural managers, cultural heritage institutions, local communities with a stake on tourism potential of their areas, policy makers and researchers on sustainable tourism and local promotion.

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News from INCULTUM Network

Policy Roundtable on 11th Oct. 2022

A policy round table was held under the aegis of EC between European Policy Makers and representatives of the six Transformations-04 call EU projects

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WEAVE Final conference

At the final conference of the WEAVE project, the key-note speech talked about INCULTUM as good practice for cultural tourism; recordings are available on website

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UNCHARTED Policy Brief

The document proposes recommendations in the area of cultural production and heritage management also focusing on the values of culture in cultural tourism development

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Visiting INCULTUM Pilots

Greece

Aos, the shared river cross-border pilot

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Albania

Vjosa, the shared river cross-border pilot

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Slovakia

Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia

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Garfagnana

San Pellegrino in Alpe, Tuscan-Emilian Apennines

France

Bibracte-Morvan: ancient paths into the future

Portugal

Agrarian coastal plain: Campina de Faro

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